

Role of HR for Improving Employee Performance through Training in Development Organizations of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT:

Human resources are the most important asset in an organization. Human resource management is the functional and strategic process through organizing, coordinating, and managing employees to achieve its mission. Human resources play a critical role in achieving organizational objectives through various initiatives including but not limited to resources planning, recruitment and selection, performance management, training and development, career planning, compensation and benefits, rewards and recognition, and employment relations. Training is one of the most effective tools to enhance employee performance and achieve organizational objectives and goals effectively and efficiently (Afroz, 2018 & Garavan, 2020). Training is a process for employees to increase their knowledge and upgrade their understanding and skills through educating employees with various tools and instructions to improve their performances. The purpose of this article is to understand the role of human resources in improving employee performances through training in development organizations of Bangladesh. Literature reviews were conducted on similar topics in different sectors and found a positive response to the hypothesis. Qualitative research has been conducted with HR professionals and employees. The result reveals that HR plays a pivotal role in organizing appropriate training and positively contributes to shaping employees' performances in the development sector. Both Functional Excellence and Soft skills training contribute to employees' job performance. Organizational internal online training also plays an important role in knowledge enhancement leading to their performance. 67% of respondents felt that there exists a fair process of selecting training participants. 60% stated that they had an online training infrastructure. 100% of respondents expressed that there was an adequate budget for training and training that played a key role in their performance. This study also sheds light on further study on different aspects of training and how do they contribute to the bottom line.

Keywords: Employee performance, career development, online training course (OLC), technical excellence, and soft skills.

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List of Abbreviations

Sl#	Abbreviations	Elaboration of the Abbreviations
1.	ADB	Asian Development Bank
2.	BCCP	Bangladesh Center for Communication Programs
3.	FAD	Financial Analysis Division
4.	FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
5.	FCDO	Foreign and Commonwealth & Development Office
6.	FPMU	Food Planning & Monitoring Unit
7.	HQ	Headquarters
8.	HRM	Human Resources
9.	HRM	Human Resources Management
10.	JASP	A Statistical Software
11.	LDC	Least Developed Country
12.	MBA	Master of Business Administration
13.	MFI	Micro Finance Institution
14.	MS	Microsoft
15.	NGO	Non-Government Organization
16.	OLC	Online Courses
17.	PKSF	Palli Karma Shayok Foundation
18.	SAPR	Semi-Annual Portfolio Review
19.	SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
20.	TNA	Training Need Assessment
21.	USAID	United States Agency for International Development
22.	WB	The World Bank

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The development sector has been playing a key role in economic emancipation in Bangladesh implementing health, education, and socioeconomic programs. Considering the current global situation where there is a sheer scarcity of resources all over the world, therefore, efficient utilization of resources has become of paramount importance these days compared to ever before. Human resource functions include many practices such as training and development, reward, job analysis, recruitment and selection, employee relationships, employee empowerment, and social support. All these practices should be built to achieve a high level of satisfaction and performance of workers (Albrecht et al., 2015; Dessler, 2006; Majumder, 2012). Training is a process to shape and equip employees by adding their skills, abilities, knowledge, and behavior, so that work can be completed more quickly, effectively, and can be done rationally (Ichsan, 2020). By being given training, employees will get specific knowledge and be able to train skills that can later be used in work (Dewi, 2019). According to Mangkunegara & Octorend, (2015) and Jumawan & Mora, (2018), there are several dimensions and indicators in training. As a result of well-trained employees, there will be less absenteeism and less wage demand. The professional skills of employees will be enhanced and trained employees will make fewer mistakes. The essential part of a worthy employee training program is constructed on orientation, management skills, and operational skills of employees which is the groundwork of any employee development program (Kleiman, 2000). Training means teaching or developing in oneself or others any skills and knowledge that relate to specific competencies. Training has specific goals of improving someone's capability, capacity, productivity, and performance. Training is a type of activity that is planned and systematic and it results in an enhanced level of skill, knowledge, and competency that are necessary to perform work effectively (Gordon, 1992). Training and development programs increase the overall performance of the organization (Shepard & Greene, 2003) although it is expensive to offer preparation to the representatives however over the long haul it gives back more than it took (Flynn, 1995 & Kaynak, 2003).

Job performance is a result of work that has been achieved by a person in carrying out tasks that have been assigned to him based on skills, experience sincerity, and time (Hasibuan, 2014 Sumenda, 2018). Adnyani & Dewi, (2019) cited that job performance is a skill possessed by an employee to perform various jobs related to job needs. One way to develop the performance possessed by employees in the company is to hold a training program in which the implemented program is made according to the needs of the company (Triasmoko, 2014). Training primarily aims to enhance employee's knowledge and skills that helps employees to perform better and eventually contribute to the bottom line and growth of the organization.

2.0 RATIONALE

Bangladesh is the eighth most populous country with 170 million population and currently, the second-largest economy in South Asia in terms of purchasing power parity. Bangladesh has impressed the world with its achievements in a relatively short span of time. ¹Being one of the poorest nations at birth, Bangladesh reached lower-middle income status in 2015 and is currently on track to graduate from the list of UN's Least Developed Countries by 2026. Its vision is to attain upper middle-income status by 2031 and developed country status by 2041. Bangladesh is implementing its Seventh Five Year Plan, and this initiative will require annual GDP growth of 7.5%-8.0%. ²Bangladesh also has a multitude of problems, and some are very crucial like education, health and nutrition, poverty, housing, and environment. In the past, most of the country's development programs tended to bypass the real beneficiaries at the implementation level and many government plans did not properly address human resources as the central element for overall development. However, innovative development practices

can play an important role for poverty reduction and the journey towards building prosperous Bangladesh and shared responsibilities between the government and development partners.

¹ The World Bank in Bangladesh, Updated: Oct 04, 2023

² Factors affecting development in Bangladesh: An approach to overcome, Jamader, N., 2019

³ Most of the poor people's problems today are significantly interrelated with shelter, food, cloth, basic education, and access to primary health care services. It is necessary to consider the benefits for poor people in development programs. However, Bangladesh aims to create jobs through a competitive business environment, efficient infrastructure, human capital, and build a skilled labor force, and establish a policy environment that attracts private investment. To start with the mainstreaming of human development, expanding people's capabilities with better health and education closing gender gap upholding human dignity. ⁴ With the youth making up 30% of its population, Bangladesh faces the critical need to bridge the gap between education and employer demands by equipping its young population with appropriate skills. To make changes happen, UNDP report makes a call to improve governance, make policies more effective, strong accountability, transparency, and rule of law.

Development sectors are working in grass-root level activities to target and empower the most disadvantaged and vulnerable populations for their socio and economic development. It tries to cover all basic needs from food, shelter, health, education, relief and rehabilitation, microcredit loan programs, rights, and governance. NGOs provide much-needed job opportunities, stimulating small enterprise development, and inspiring people from a traditionally agricultural society to pursue non-farm service-oriented livelihoods. The non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have been playing supportive roles with the government. In some cases, they are considered more effective to get attached to the grass-root-level developmental initiatives. The roles and initiatives played by the NGOs in Bangladesh have been considered as having positive impacts on poverty alleviation among the rural poor population. In areas where the poverty situation remains intense, NGO activities typically get more importance.

³ ADB: 'Asian Development Bank: Basic Statistics'. 2018

⁴ New directions for human development in Bangladesh: UNDP Bangladesh, 19 December 2023

A lot of research conducted on training and employee performance in different sectors of Bangladesh. However, the development sector falls behind in this respect due to inadequate HR practices, the lack of management attention or focus, and inadequate professional people currently undertaking HR responsibilities. It is also observed that HR functions are commonly managed by employees from other disciplines especially admin and finance cadres in the development sector in Bangladesh, especially in local NGOs. In some cases, centrally managed HR business partners undertake routine functions, and strategic HR functions are managed at the HQ level.

The rationale of this study is very pertinent to analyze the roles of HR in development organizations of Bangladesh and the impact of training on improving employee performance. Due to the nature of operations, the development sector operates with a lot of flexibility, and HR functions are being played by employees with different backgrounds, effective training plans are not formulated aligned with organization strategies. Training opportunities become available in an ad-hoc manner and relatively junior employees get less priority for appropriate training related to their job requirements. However, their job performances are achieved through formal education and support from senior colleagues and peers. However, job

performance can be improved through technical excellence (in-person or online courses) and soft skills training.

3.0 OBJECTIVES & RESEARCH PROBLEM

3.1 Research Objectives:

This study aims to help understand the role of Human Resources management in planning and organizing appropriate training for employees in consultation with the management and the line managers on how to implement effective training courses for employees, also, how these training courses could help employees improve their performance. Also, to investigate the impact of training and development on employee performance in different development organizations in Bangladesh, International development organizations, and bilateral/ multi-lateral development organizations like BCCP, PKSf, USAID, FCDO, SIDA, and the World Bank) to identify the perceptions of the employee and how training was beneficial for their performance improvement. To explore Human Resource Management practices within development organizations and to analyze the importance of training for employees. Examining and elaborating the determined factors and barriers in the areas in ensuring impactful training for the employees. Analyze the views of the employees regarding HR and training for their career development. To suggest appropriate HR policies to impart training for employees' performance in the development sector of Bangladesh.

3.2 Assumptions:

This study assumes that there is a predominant role of HR to ensure appropriate training for employees in development organizations. There is a positive and significant relationship between training and employee performance. Various literature reviews and hypothesis testing show that training significantly affects employees' job performance. This means that if the training for employees is improved, the employee's work performance will also increase. Conversely, if the training is not improved, employees' work performance will also decrease. The findings of this study are the findings of previous studies conducted by Mashar, W., (2015) which shows that there is a significant influence between training and work performance (Awal & Abrian, (2020). Training can improve employee work performance, which in turn can improve the employee's career development as well. Companies that often conduct training for employees will increase employee work performance and employees will be more motivated to work so that company goals can be achieved Niati, D. R, Siregar, Z. M. E., Prayoga, Y., (2021). Therefore, the current study envisages a strong role of HR in ensuring appropriate training for employee performance particularly in the development sector of Bangladesh.

3.3 Research Problem:

The research problem is the statement of knowledge gap or fundamental challenge in a field. It refers to a gap in the existing knowledge that a researcher aims to address in their research consisting of specific questions that require appropriate investigation and analysis of the subject. It comprises of well-defined questions which is the starting point of the research topic. It involves several steps including identifying a broad research topic, learning more about the problem, identifying the relevant variables and how they are related, thinking practical aspect, formulating the problem statement, sticking to plans with flexibility. Later, conducted literature review, refining the research questions, developing a research hypothesis, defining the scope and limitations. A well-formulated research problem ensures a clear definition of the specific problem manageable withing a stipulated time, resources, and overall scope, relevance to the field of study and contributes to the existing set-up. It helps the researcher design the methodologies, collect data, analyze the results in a systematic manner. The research problems

questions cultivating critical thinking and hones problem solving skills using research methods. Research problem characterizes Novel, significant, feasible, clear, and specific and rooted in evidence.

3.3.1 Research Problem

What are the roles of HR in ensuring training to improve employees' performance in selected development organizations of Bangladesh?

3.3.2 Sub-questions

- What are the key roles of HR in the development sector in Bangladesh?
- How does organizational training contribute to the employees' performances?

4.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

There has been a lot of research on training focusing on employee performance in different sectors (garments, banks, and manufacturing industries) in Bangladesh. However, there is very limited research on Human Resources especially in the development sector of Bangladesh focusing on training and employee performance. This study will try to facilitate identifying relevant theories, methods, and gaps in existing research undertaking a review of relevant research articles published in recent years, especially during last 5 years to provide the foundation of knowledge on the subject. Hidayat & Budiartma (2018) observed that job training programs affect the performance of employees at the workplace. Tukunimulongo (2016) also observed that on-the-job training has an impact on employee performance. Koo et al., (2020) argued that if employees perceive that there has been a dearth of promotion opportunities, they might be dissatisfied with their current jobs. The following literatures have been reviewed (in tabular format):

Sl#	Study Focus	Authors & Title	Year	Research Method	Result
1.	Effectiveness of Training and Development on Employee Performance	Mitu, F. et al., “The Effectiveness of Training and Development on Employee Performance at Private Commercial Banks in Bangladesh: SEM Approach”	2017	A structured questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1 strongly disagree to 5 (strongly agree) was used.	Training and Development have a positive effect on employee performance. Training and development have imposed a positive impact on employee performance in the context of the private commercial banking sector of Dhaka in Bangladesh. It can help create a sustainable competitive advantage over other key players. The Bank should develop a sound training and development process where the performance of employees is

					evaluated through transparent systems.
2.	Training and Development Programs on Employee Performance	Karim, R. A. "Impact of Different Training and Development Programs on Employee Performance in Bangladesh Perspective" In the International Journal of Entrepreneurial Research.	2019	Face-to-face survey through a structured questionnaire with predefined answers. The sample size of this study is only 100 which may not be representative of the whole population.	The findings indicate that there is a positive relationship between training and development practices and employee performance. Organizations that invest in their employee skills by way of training and development activities will certainly reap the profits through productivity.
3.	Training and Development on Employee Performance	Mamy, M. M. B., Shabbir, R., & Hasan, M. Z. "The Influence of Training and Development on Employee Performance: A Study on Garments Sector, Dhaka Bangladesh"	2020	Primary data was collected by interviewing employees working in garment industries through a structured questionnaire using quantitative and qualitative techniques.	Quality and relevant training and development programs should be organized in a way to meets employees' expectations or improves productivity.
4	Impact of training and development program on employee performance	Chowdhury, H. J. & Uddin, K., "Impact of training and development program on employee performance: a	2022	Conducted survey of 50 employees in various state-owned commercial bank branches. The questionnaire was developed to collect primary survey data	Almost all the employees of state-owned commercial banks consider training and development an important element of their performance. Most of the employees think

		study on state own commercial banks of Bangladesh".		using the Likert scale.	that training and development processes are not maintained properly and providing procedures does not make a fruitful which are required to perform their jobs.
5	Promotion and Job Training on Job Satisfaction of Employees	Atikur R., & UDDIN, M. U., "The Effect of Promotion and Job Training on Job Satisfaction of Employees: An Empirical Study of the SME Sector in Bangladesh".	2022	Data was collected from Dhaka-based SME firms working with employees from Bangladesh, followed by the purposive sampling method. A Likert-scale questionnaire was used.	Job training and promotion positively impact the SME employee's current job profiles and their overall satisfaction while working in the SME business sector.

In conclusion, there is a need for further study on the role of Human Resources in the development sector in Bangladesh to identify the gap in this research area. There is a need for additional research work to identify the relationship of existing works in the context of its contribution to the topic within existing literature and why further study is needed. A well-structured questionnaire based on some questions related to the role of HR and the impact of training in the development sector of Bangladesh will be used in my study. Therefore, the research on development organizations can bring new food for thought in further research.

5.0 RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a logical and systematic plan to identify, select and analyze information about a specific topic. Qualitative research using Delphi Method has been conducted on primary data. It is a systematic and qualitative method of forecasting by collecting opinions from a group of experts through several rounds of interviews. Delphi aimed to achieve a consensus based on discussion with experts through face-to-face meetings or interviews to obtain experts' opinion in the field of research to enhance the sense of the subject and analyze the factors in terms of understanding the subject. It consists of 2-3 rounds of written questionnaires that allow experts to give their opinions. After the experts answered each round of questionnaires, all the answers were collected, and a summary report of the answers was sent to each expert. Special attention has been paid to the selection of experts to avoid methodological weakness and ensure validity and reliability of the results.

5.1 Population:

Heterogeneous purposeful sampling was used since there are different types and sizes of organizations with a sample size of 15 for the in-depth interviews.

5.2 Validity Assessment Method:

Content validity describes whether all aspects and dimensions are relevant and reduces bias from one person for the research problem at the highest possible level.

5.3 Reliability Assessment Method:

Reliability is the extent to which the questions used in a survey instrument consistently elicit the same results each time it is asked (after pre-testing) in the same situation on repeated occasions. Cronbach's alpha measured the internal consistency reliability. Semi structured questionnaire has been developed to collect the primary survey data was divided into two parts. The first part consists of personal information like Age, Gender, and Employee Level. The second part of the questionnaire includes questions relating to HR and training of different views that the employees feel observe or experience as qualitative information. There are five points of the response which has developed in a ranging scale from "Strongly agree=5 to Strongly disagree=1" with some open questions where the employees can give feedback based on their wishes. There is no restriction on answering or collecting the information.

5.4 Scope and Limitation:

There are some challenges and limitations that need to be considered when evaluating the validity and reliability of a selection test or interview. Validity and reliability are not fixed properties of a test or interview but depend on the context, the purpose, and the population of the candidates. Validity and reliability are not mutually exclusive, but interrelated and complementary. A test or interview can be reliable but not valid, or valid but not reliable. Validity and reliability are not sufficient, but necessary conditions for a good selection test or interview. However, though necessary precautionary measures have been taken there could be the existence of sources of error or bias such as sampling error and non-response error and influence of question wording and format. Also, results can be affected by respondent motivation, availability, and willingness. There are other considerations such as insufficient sample size for statistical measurements, lack of previous research studies on the topic, limited access to data due to the sensitive nature of the study, and time constraints.

6.0 FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Development organizations having strong HR teams are in a better position to organize effective training for their employees. Medium to large development organizations having functional HR organize training after conducting TNA. However, small to medium-sized local NGOs do not have dedicated HR teams to undertake training for their employees. The result was analyzed by using statistical software JASP, MS Excel, and percentage analysis on a five-point Rating Scale.

Descriptive Statistics (Table 1):									
	Age	Gender	Position Level	Years (Current Job)	Have a HR	HR Role on Trg.	Overall HR Capacity	Trg. in 1 year	Trg. Positive Impact
Valid	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	44.60	0.2667	2.000	11.10	0.9333	3.133	3.467	2.400	1.000
Mode	30.00	0.000	2.000	3.000	1.000	3.000	4.000	1.000	1.000
Std. Deviation	12.18	0.4577	0.7559	9.431	0.2582	0.9155	0.8338	1.121	0.000
Skewness	0.2376	1.176	0.000	1.071	-3.873	-0.2931	-2.012	0.1123	NaN
Std. Error of Skewness	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801	0.5801

Descriptive Statistics (Table 1):

	Age	Gender	Position Level	Years (Current Job)	Have a HR	HR Role on Trg.	Overall HR Capacity	Trg. in 1 year	Trg. Positive Impact
Kurtosis	-1.645	-0.7343	-1.077	0.4982	15.00	1.894	4.867	-1.291	NaN
Std. Error of Kurtosis	1.121	1.121	1.121	1.121	1.121	1.121	1.121	1.121	1.121
Minimum	30.00	0.000	1.000	1.500	0.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Maximum	62.00	1.000	3.000	33.00	1.000	5.000	4.000	4.000	1.000

^a More than one mode exists, only the first is reported

Frequencies:

Frequencies for Gender (Table 2):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	11	73.3	73.3	73.3
1	4	26.7	26.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

0=Female and 1= Male

Frequencies for Employee Position Level (Table 3):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	26.7	26.7	26.7
2	7	46.7	46.7	73.3
3	4	26.7	26.7	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

1= Junior level, 2=Mid-Level and 3=Senior Level

Frequencies for Having a Dedicated HR (Table 4):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	1	6.7	6.7	6.7
1	14	93.3	93.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

0=No Dedicated HR and 1=Have Dedicated HR

Frequencies for HR Role in Training (Table 5):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	6.7	6.7	6.7
2	1	6.7	6.7	13.3
3	9	60.0	60.0	73.3
4	3	20.0	20.0	93.3
5	1	6.7	6.7	100.0

Frequencies for HR Role in Training (Table 5):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Frequencies for Overall HR Capacity (Table 6):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	1	6.7	6.7	6.7
3	5	33.3	33.3	40.0
4	9	60.0	60.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Scale: “Strongly agree=5 to Strongly disagree=1”

Frequencies for Training in 1 year (Table 7):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	4	26.7	26.7	26.7
2	4	26.7	26.7	53.3
3	4	26.7	26.7	80.0
4	3	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

Frequencies for Positive Impact of Training (Table 8):

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1	15	100.0	100.0	100.0
Total	15	100.0	100.0	

1=Positive of Training

Plots-Age: (Figure 1)

Employee Position Level (Figure 2)

Years with Current Employer (Figure 3):

Have a dedicated HR (Figure 4)

HR Role in Training (Figure 5)

Overall HR Capacity (Figure 6)

Training in 1 year (Figure 7)

Chi-Square Test:

After carrying out the data collection the average results are pooled (see below table) to determine whether there is an association between HR Training, Overall HR role, and Training in the last 1 year amongst males and females (**Table 9**):

Gender	HR Training Role	Overall HR	Training 1 year	Total
Male	3.00	3.55	2.45	9.00
Female	3.50	3.25	2.25	9.00
Grand Total	6.50	6.80	4.70	18.00

Expected values (E) for Male and Female respondents are shown below (**Table 10**):

Gender	HR Training Role	Overall HR	Training 1 year	Total
Male	3.25	3.40	2.35	9.00
Female	3.25	3.40	2.35	9.00
Grand Total	6.50	6.80	4.70	18.00

Now, the Chi-Square value using the Formula: $(O-E)^2/E$ (**Table 11**)

Male	0.02	0.01	0.00
Female	0.02	0.01	0.00

Chi-Square statistics $0.02+0.01+0.00+0.02+0.01+0.00=0.06$. We compared this to a Chi-Square table with a degree of freedom 2. The corresponding X^2 value is 0.051 and the P value is 0.975.

Reliability Analysis: Scale Reliability Statistics (Table 12)

	sd	Cronbach's α
scale	4.194	0.084

Note. Of the observations, 15 were used, 0 were excluded, and 15 were provided.

We observed that the respondents' mean age was 45 years (44.6 years). Minimum age of 30 years and the maximum age of 62 years with a Standard deviation of 12.18 represented by 27% Females and 63% Males. The level of employees was 4 at junior level, 7 at mid-level, and 4 at senior level with little over 11 (11.10) years working with the current employer. Cronbach's Alpha 0.084 is acceptable. The Chi-Square Statistics on Males and Females for Overall HR Roles, HR Roles on Training, and Number of Training in the last year was 0.06. We compared this to a Chi-Square Table on the Degree of Freedom 2. The corresponding X^2 value is 0.051 and the P value is 0.975. Because 0.06 is less than 0.97.5, therefore, we must accept that there is an association between Male and Female respondents. Males rated HR Role for Training 3 and Females rated 3.5. However, on overall HR capacity, Males rated 3.55 and females rated 3.25 and the number of trainings during last year was 2.4 and 2.25 respectively. Relatively young and junior to mid-level employees aged between (30 to 45) attended 3 or more training during the last year. Whereas senior employees aged 46 years and above attended a maximum of two courses during the last year. This indicates that the relatively young employees have more interest and/or opportunity to attend training. 20% of respondents feel challenged attending training. However, 67% of respondents feel that there exists a fair selection process within the organization for training participants. 60% of respondents mentioned that they had an online training infrastructure in their organizations. One positive sign in the development sector is that 100% of respondents expressed that there is an adequate budget for training. Everyone mentioned that training played a key role in their performance improvement.

Therefore, it is evident that through adequate and effective training, employee performance improves. On average, respondents rated 3 on a five-point scale (1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree) on HR's critical role in organization training. However, they rated 3.5 on the

overall HR performance in their respective organization. Training is one of the key roles that HR plays along with (a) Recruitment and Selection, (b) Payroll administration, (c) Performance appraisal, (d) Employment terms and conditions, and (e) Policy compliance.

They also mentioned that staff received more than 2 (2.4) training during the last year. 7 respondents (47%) mentioned that HR undertakes training needs assessment in consultation with concerned staff/department. 27% of respondents recommended soft skills training, 27% Functional training, 20% TNA, and the rest 46% recommended various other training. Human Resources plays an important role in organizing appropriate training in development organizations in Bangladesh. Most of the trainings positively contribute to shaping employees' performances. Organizational internal Online Courses (OLC) play an important role in employees' performance improvement. Further studies may be needed to understand the extent of training required for different levels of employees.

7.0 PROPOSED MODEL / FRAMEWORK (Figure-8):

8.0 CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

Employees become more skillful, and their work productivity increases so as their performance, when HR plays a critical and effective role in organizing appropriate training for them. Employees remain committed and motivated when they are appropriately trained to achieving organizational goals and objectives which interns contribute to the bottom line. Training is a process involving various tools, instructions, and activities designed to gain or increase their knowledge and upgrade their understanding and skills to improve employee performance. Human resources play a strategic and coherent approach to effectively managing people in an organization to help achieving business and to gain a competitive advantage. Training is considered one of the most important functions of HR equally beneficial for both employee and employer. Organizations need to improve the skills and abilities of employees so that employees are better equipped with knowledge and skills for doing their jobs effectively and efficiently. It is evident that training has a positive impact on employee performance in the development sector of Bangladesh. Inhouse training such as “Technical excellence” and “Soft skills” trainings are the most impactful trainings for employee performance improvement. HR plays a pivotal role in arranging such training for employees. The more efficiently HR functions, the more effective training an organization can provide/ arrange to increase their employee performance. Generally, it takes quite a bit of time to get the actual benefit of employee training. In the real term, training is considered as investing in people!

However, it was not possible to identify the extent of the impact that training provides on employee performance due to time limitations. Future research endeavors may also explore the extent of knowledge gained in different training courses with comparative studies across other countries to gain a comprehensive understanding of how training impacts employee performances in one country compared to others. How frequently should training be imparted to an individual to get the maximum benefits?

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